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METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES**Chariyeva Dinora Jumanazarovna**

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Annotation. This article examines the methodology of teaching foreign languages, the historical development of this field as a science, the various modern techniques employed in foreign language instruction, and their practical applications.

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются методика преподавания иностранных языков, историческое развитие этой области как науки, различные современные методики обучения иностранным языкам и их практическое применение.

Ключевые слова: методология, инновация, иностранный язык, общение, умения, компетенции, дидактика, межкультурная коммуникация.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish metodikasi, fan sifatida ushbu sohaning tarixiy rivojlanishi, chet tilini o'qitishda qo'llaniladigan turli zamonaviy texnikalar va ularning amaliy qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: metodologiya, innovatsiya, chet tili, muloqot, malaka, malaka, didaktika, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

Modern advancements in education have led to the emergence of innovative pedagogy. The term "innovative" translates to "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. American researcher E. Rogers explored the socio-psychological aspect of innovation, examining the classification of participants, their attitudes towards new developments, and other factors. The concepts of novelty and innovation differ in scientific fields. "Innovation" refers to new tools, methods, methodologies, and technologies, while the innovation process progresses through specific stages in education. As global science continually advances, this positive trend has also impacted our country. Advanced innovative technologies are being integrated into our scientific community. Consequently, our President declared this year as the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health," increasing the responsibility of our nation's youth. The widespread adoption of modern, innovative technologies in

education has opened numerous opportunities and goals for young people learning foreign languages.

The methodology of foreign language teaching as a science has over 200 years of history. Throughout this period, various perspectives on foreign language teaching methodology have emerged. One such perspective comes from academician L.V. Shcherba. He believed that while the methodology of teaching any subject is practical, it is not purely theoretical. It addresses practical issues. Specifically, the methodology of foreign language teaching is based not only on psychological evidence but also on general and specific linguistic studies. Linguistics examines the origin and movement laws of language phenomena, while methodology addresses the practical application of these phenomena based on linguistic laws. The most valuable methodology books are written by linguists, including G. Sweet, a notable 19th-century phonetician and English linguist, O. Jespersen, a distinguished phonetician and theoretical linguist in late 19th and early 20th-century England, and prominent French linguists like F. Brunot and M. Bréal. In Russia, academician L.V. Shcherba, his mentor, the great linguist I.A. Baudouin de Courtenay, and their students focused on language teaching methodology. Psychologists hold a different view on foreign language teaching methodology. Professor V.A. Artemov commented on the relationship between methodology and psychology, suggesting that psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology examines how teachers conduct lessons, while psychology studies how students learn the subject. However, this perspective is not entirely agreeable since both teachers and students inevitably encounter and are influenced by psychological processes and states during teaching and learning.

Method Without Translation: Historically, various forms of this method are recognized. They can be classified into two main groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language naturally should mimic the conditions of acquiring one's mother tongue. The primary goal of this method is the idea that by learning to speak a foreign language, one can also learn to read and write. A key principle of the natural method is to create a language environment. Different approaches have emerged in the practical application of these advanced methodological principles, evident in the creative efforts of the method's proponents.

The new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education is largely based on pragmatic linguistics research, which views language as a field of human activity rather than merely a system of linguistic forms. Since the early

1970s, new conclusions in this field have sparked intense discussions about educational goal setting. New curricula were adopted, aiming to "teach students to communicate," or "Befaeigung zur Kommunikation" (communicative competence). In the 1970s, the "communicative method" was validated through several stages of attempts, advancing the science of methodology. Mastering any foreign language requires a deep understanding of its methodology. The method of "communicative didactics" is also crucial in the methodology of foreign language teaching.

Communicative didactics: Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline involving complex psychological changes, particularly the comparison of the native language with a foreign language. Various teaching methods and technologies are employed in this process. Modern pedagogical technologies enhance the effectiveness of teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue. Teaching a foreign language necessitates knowledge of its methodology, which is vital in the learning process. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology include the communicative didactic method, the intercultural dialogue organization method, and the exercise organization method. These methods are interrelated and complementary. The science of methodology, being connected to the science of didactics, emphasizes communicativeness in foreign language learning, leading to the development of the communicative didactics method.

Methodology and technologies play a crucial role in the process of learning a foreign language. Various teaching methodologies are employed in this field. The most widely used methods include the communicative didactic method, the intercultural dialogue organization method, and the exercise organization method. These three methods are closely interrelated and complement each other. Since the science of methodology is connected to the science of didactics, it emphasizes communicativeness in foreign language learning, leading to the development of the communicative didactics method.

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